

Socio-demographic factors associated with non-adherents to TB treatment in South Africa

Lucky Norah Katende-Kyenda¹

¹ Walter Sisulu University, Department of Medicine and Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, School of Medicine, Sissons Street, Fortgale, Mthatha, Eastern Cape, South Africa

Corresponding author: Lucky Norah Katende-Kyenda (nkatende-kyenda@wsu.ac.za)

Received 14 October 2025 ♦ Accepted 28 February 2026 ♦ Published 22 April 2026

Citation: Katende-Kyenda LN (2026) Socio-demographic factors associated with non-adherents to TB treatment in South Africa. *Pharmacia* 73: e174871. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e174871>

Abstract

Non-adherence to tuberculosis treatment is the main obstacle to its eradication worldwide, with 40% of patients reported in under-developed nations. The current study aimed to determine socio-demographic factors associated with non-adherents to TB treatment at a healthcare center in South Africa. A cross-sectional study was conducted on 65 patients undergoing treatment. Socio-demographic and non-adherence data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS. Association between socio-demographic factors and non-adherents was obtained using Pearson chi-square tests and adjusted odds ratios, with $p \leq 0.05$ regarded as statistically significant. The mean age of participants was 36.23 ± 11.21 years, with 41 (63.08%) males and 24 (36.92%) females, with 40% between the ages of 26 and 35. Unmarried individuals were 53 (81.53%), with a high-school level of education. There were 35 unemployed patients (53.84%), and 35 (53.80%) were HIV seronegative. Adherents to the treatment were 45 (69.23%), while 20 (30.77%) were non-adherents participants. Gender and unemployment were associated with non-adherence. A significant correlation was found between unemployment ($X^2 = 41.838, p = 0.047$) and non-adherence, as well as gender and non-adherence ($X^2 = 10.604, p < 0.001$). Non-adherence to TB treatment was associated with socio-demographic factors; therefore, understanding these factors may help establish more effective policies targeting patients at risk.

Keywords

Adherence, primary healthcare, socio-demographics, TB drugs, tuberculosis

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), there were an estimated 10.8 million people globally living with tuberculosis (TB) in 2023. Of these, only 8.2 million cases were notified (which is almost 76% treatment coverage) (WHO 2025). TB notification increased from 7.5 million in the previous year. It was estimated that 400,000 people developed multidrug-resistant and rifampicin-resistant TB (MDR/RR-TB) in 2023, yet only 175,923 (44%) people were started on treatment for MDR/RR-TB during the same year.

TB was predicted to have a mortality rate of 1.25 million in 2023, placing it among the top 10 causes of death globally after three years, when coronavirus disease (COVID-19) overtook TB as the leading cause of death from a single infectious agent. This included 161,000 people with HIV (WHO 2025). TB has a significant impact on the African continent, accounting for 403,000 (32%) deaths and 24% of the global TB burden in 2023 (WHO 2024a). It was also the leading cause of death for people living with HIV and the main cause of antibiotic-resistant mortality.

A recent report (WHO report of 2024) states that South Africa (SA) has a particularly high burden of TB, experiencing one of the most severe epidemics in the world. This is a major public health challenge (WHO 2024b). In 2023, an estimated 427 new TB cases per 100,000 people were reported, and TB was the top infectious killer disease globally that year, with 56,000 deaths. As investigated in their study, Oamen et al. (2024) reported that in SA, TB is a leading cause of illness and mortality. Poor adherence to TB therapy is linked to socioeconomic and socio-demographic characteristics.

As stated by Leketa et al. (2024), studies on socio-demographic factors influencing TB treatment adherence are highly valuable because they identify vulnerable populations who are at high risk of non-adherence, for example, people with low socioeconomic status or inadequate social support. Kamangu and Mboweni (2024) say that it is imperative to understand demographic groups' unique adherence challenges, such as the physical, psychological, and socio-cultural factors affecting adolescents or the socioeconomic barriers faced by older people. This allows public health programs to design targeted interventions, such as tailored educational materials, modified treatment regimens, or specialized support services, thereby improving health outcomes and addressing disparities.

To take preventative measures, it is also essential to be aware of the disease. *Bacillus mycobacterium* is the infectious agent that causes TB (Amiri et al. 2021). TB normally affects the lungs, but it can also affect other parts of the body, according to the WHO coronavirus disease (COVID-19) surveillance database (Falzon et al. 2023).

TB is the most common infectious disease in the world and a major threat to public health. According to the WHO and the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) (2024), TB is preventable and can be treated, but it nevertheless exists in all nations and age categories, with eight countries accounting for about half of all cases. It spreads because of factors such as poverty, overcrowding, and a lack of access to healthcare. The COVID-19 epidemic also caused problems with diagnosis and treatment, which resulted in an increase in cases.

Even after the Directly Observed Treatment Strategy (DOTS) program was implemented in 1995, TB remains a significant health issue in SA, particularly in the Eastern Cape (EC) (Katende-Kyenda 2025). Despite recent declines in TB-related mortality and a decline in TB incidence since 2009, TB continues to be the leading cause of death in SA. There is a decrease in TB infections and related problems when adherence to treatment and its difficulties are understood. According to Religioni et al. (2025), adherence to therapy, or the extent to which a patient complies with suggested treatment recommendations, is essential for the effective management of chronic diseases, such as diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular disorders. Non-adherence is the primary barrier to anti-TB therapy (ATT), leading to multidrug resistance (MDR) and chronic drug-resistant TB.

Although WHO (2025) recommends an 85% TB cure rate, the EC reported a far lower cure rate of 41%, which was below the national average and the minimum pro-

posed threshold of the WHO of 65%. The EC of SA has a high incidence and prevalence of TB cases, as well as notably low cure rates (Faye et al. 2024). Effective TB therapy management requires adherence to ATT, which involves complex issues that make care for TB patients difficult. Non-adherence to ATT results in poor treatment outcomes, increased morbidity, a weak economy, high mortality, relapses, development of medicine resistance, and increased disease transmission (Tirore et al. 2024).

By understanding the socio-demographic barriers to adherence, interventions can be tailored to address them. This may involve providing culturally sensitive education, offering transportation support, or implementing peer support programs. According to Nidoi et al. (2021), people's varied socio-cultural practices, which are exacerbated by high rates of poverty (74.2%) and poor literacy (33%), also have a detrimental impact on the use of health services and their results.

The Centers for Disease Control (CDC) and Prevention conclude that TB patients who are started on treatment but do not achieve the intended results may die, become drug-resistant, and may spread the disease across their community (CDC 2025). In their study on using economic assistance to enhance TB treatment outcomes in SA, Nidoi et al. (2021) conclude that poverty not only increases the chance of developing TB but also affects the results of TB treatment in low-income nations. According to earlier research performed by Gebremariam et al. (2021), 50% of people in India (Gwalani et al. 2025), 15.5% in Thailand (Kamolwat et al. 2021), 35% in Africa (Oamen et al. 2024), and 19.5% in Ethiopia (Yene et al. 2025) do not take their ATT as prescribed.

A major risk factor for TB treatment failure, relapse, and the emergence of drug-resistant strains of the disease, such as MDR-TB and XDR-TB, is poor patient adherence to ATT. According to Zereabruk et al. (2024), patients frequently do not finish the entire 6-month course of therapy and are not aware of how important it is to have follow-up sputum re-examinations. Non-adherence stems from various factors, including inadequate knowledge about TB, poor patient education, adverse drug side effects, logistical challenges such as transportation costs, lack of social support, and fear of stigma (Tirore et al. 2024). Other factors include co-morbidities such as smoking, alcohol use, being far from a medical facility, a lack of family and staff support, or a treatment plan. Shinde (2024) agrees that socio-demographic characteristics such as age, gender, income, and educational attainment are associated with non-adherence to TB treatment.

According to certain writers, DR-TB is independently linked to living in a one-room house (Biru and Woldesemayat 2020). The illness was more likely to strike those with low incomes and little exposure to schooling. Poverty-induced poor nutrition may be associated with a poor immune system that increases susceptibility. Poverty also often results in congested areas, poor ventilation, and unhygienic conditions, all of which increase the risk of tuberculosis transmission.

Health inequalities are associated with social determinants of health, such as racism, stigma, poverty, uneven access to

healthcare, and illiteracy. For instance, the stigma associated with TB may discourage people from getting medical attention or follow-up treatments for it when they are ill.

Identifying high-risk groups is important. The initial wave of the COVID-19 pandemic and the lockdowns disrupted global healthcare systems (Omar et al. 2024). The current study can pinpoint specific populations who are more likely to experience challenges with TB treatment adherence. This will allow for tailored interventions and support systems for these vulnerable groups. Improving treatment outcomes is significant for this study because, by addressing socio-demographic barriers to adherence, researchers can contribute to improving TB treatment outcomes, leading to reduced TB transmission, fewer deaths, and a stronger public health response, as revealed by the Centers for Disease Control (CDC) and Prevention of TB (2025).

The research question of this study was: Which socio-demographic characteristics are linked to non-adherence to anti-tuberculosis treatment in patients attending a primary healthcare environment in EC, South Africa?

A conceptual model known as a theoretical framework is a conceptual model or theory that is used to guide this research. In this study, the framework helped to organize and understand the socio-demographic factors causing patients not to adhere to their medication regimen (Arakelyan et al. 2021). The theoretical framework that has been used in this study is the Health Belief Model (HBM). The author used the framework to formulate the research question on non-adherence to TB medication.

HBM explains how a patient's perceived severity of TB and belief in treatment effectiveness influence his or her adherence to the treatment (Karat et al. 2021). The theoretical framework acts as a lens to help researchers identify, organize, and explain potential reasons for non-adherence (Unni and Bae 2022). This can stem from individual factors (such as beliefs and symptoms), social circumstances (such as stigma and support), and health system issues (such as access and communication).

The aim of this study was to evaluate the socio-demographic characteristics linked to non-adherence to TB treatment in a public PHC in South Africa. The primary goal was achieved through the following particular goals, which were to:

- Identify the socio-demographic characteristics of TB patients who come to the clinic.
- Determine the prevalence of non-adherence to TB therapy.
- Identify socio-demographic variables associated with non-adherence to ATT.
- Evaluate medication-related variables and patient programs that impact non-adherence.

Methodology

The researcher followed an application of a theoretical framework in this section of the methodology. In general, the theoretical framework has been applied in providing a structured approach to understanding the complex in-

terplay of factors (such as the individual patient and the social, structural, and healthcare issues) influencing adherence, leading to more focused research, systematic data collection, and the development of evidence-based interventions. A framework has been applied to ensure that the research questions are relevant (Arakelyan et al. 2021). Afterwards, the data analysis and the findings have been integrated into a coherent explanation of non-adherence, ultimately improving the reliability and validity of the study.

Study design, setting, and population

Study design

Socio-demographic factors associated with non-adherence to ATT in TB patients who visited a PHC in South Africa in June 2023 were identified using a quantitative cross-sectional approach. To uncover socio-demographic characteristics linked to non-adherence to TB treatment in a PHC in South Africa, the researchers used a cross-sectional design, which is suitable for this kind of study because it permits data to be collected at a single moment in time.

Study setting

The study was carried out from June to August 2023 at the Mthatha Gateway Clinic in the EC, which is a TB clinic run by the public primary health institution in Mthatha. Southridge, Fortgale, Lindale, Qweqwe, Ultra City, Slovo, Mandela Park, Chris Hani, Payne, and Zimbane are among the local communities served by the Mthatha Gateway Clinic. The medical facility is open from 07:00 until 16:00 on weekdays. The nine departments of the clinic are the pharmacy, antenatal care, family planning, chronic conditions (HPT, DM, HIV/AIDS, and epilepsy), men's clinic, minor ailments, decanting, and the dental clinic.

Study population

The study population were all patients who were receiving ATT from Mthatha Gateway Clinic in the EC for at least 1 month.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria of the selected patients

Inclusion criteria

Patients who were included in the study were:

- Those who were on ATT for at least 1 month before the study period in June 2023 and ongoing, collecting their TB treatment from Mthatha Gateway Clinic;
- Those above the age of 18 years;
- Both male and female patients on ATT; and
- People of all races.

Exclusion criteria

The following patients were excluded from taking part in the study:

- Patients who had started their treatment outside the defined time period;
- Individuals who have additional current illnesses, such as MDR-TB or XDR-TB;
- Participants with severe illnesses or those with hearing or speaking difficulties;
- Those with cognitive impairments that affected their understanding; and
- Patients without TB.

Sample size determination and sampling strategy

Sample size calculation

- The sample size was calculated using Slovin's formula (Johnson 2025) [28]: $n = N/(1 + Ne^2)$, where: n = sample size, N = population size = 280,
- e = margin of error (<10%) = 0.09;
- $n = N/(1 + Ne^2)$;
- $n = 280 / (1 + 280 \times (0.09^2)) = 280 / (1 + 280 \times 0.0081) = 280 / (1 + 2.268)$;
- $n = 280 / (1 + 280 \times 0.0081) = 280 / (1 + 280 \times 0.0081) = 280 / (1 + 2.268)$;
- $n = 280 / 3.268 = 85.67 = 86$.

Therefore, our sample size was supposed to be 86 patients, but during the data collection only 65 patients were available.

Sampling strategy

To find participants for this study, a convenient sampling strategy was used at the healthcare facility. The viability and accessibility of this non-probability sampling technique in contacting a large number of participants over the research period led to its selection. This approach is commonly used in studies on non-adherence to ATT because it allows researchers to focus on certain groups or individuals who are most likely to gain insight into the factors contributing to non-adherence.

Study variables

Dependent variables

Non-adherence to anti-TB drugs.

Independent variables

Socio-demographic factors included factors such as gender (male or female), age (18–25, 26–35, 36–45, 46–55, >55), marital status (single, married), educational status (high school with tertiary education), monthly income

(unemployed, 1000–3000, >3001–5000, >5000), and HIV status (seropositive and seronegative). Patient-related factors included staff support, family support, the distance to travel to the clinic, substance abuse, unemployment, drug-related factors included side effects, and drug shortage. A non-adherent patient to TB treatment was defined as a patient who missed at least one scheduled dose of his or her prescribed TB treatment.

Data collection tool and procedure

Application of theoretical framework in guiding data collection

The theoretical framework helped to determine what data were to be collected by focusing on specific categories of factors, such as psychological perceptions (Health Belief Model) or multi-level influences (WHO-MAM).

Questionnaire

A standardized questionnaire was developed to evaluate non-adherence to anti-TB drugs and the factors that influence it. The questionnaire included questions regarding the demographic characteristics of patients. It was initially written in English and then translated into isiXhosa to guarantee consistency. At the TB clinic, data were collected by students using an interviewer-administered questionnaire in a calm setting when patients arrived for follow-up care.

Validity and reliability of the questionnaire

Structured questionnaires aim for both validity and reliability.

Validity of the questionnaire

Validity of a questionnaire refers to its accuracy and truthfulness in measuring what it is intended to measure (Ranganathan et al. 2024).

Reliability of a questionnaire

The reliability of a questionnaire refers to its ability to produce the same results consistently when administered under the same conditions over time (Mo et al. 2023). Reliability is generally considered high in structured questionnaires because of the use of standardized, closed-ended questions.

Data collection procedure

Data quality control

Data collectors were trained for 2 days regarding the goals of the study, when to collect data, how to conduct interviews, how to contact respondents, and how to keep information private afterwards. The lead investigator kept an eye on the whole data-gathering procedure and

checked for consistency every day. Any problems that came up were handled properly. Non-adherence to ATT was obtained through self-report questions.

Data processing and analysis

Data management

This is the process of gathering, arranging, safeguarding, and preserving patients' data so that it may be examined and comprehended. Data management was closely followed in these ways.

Data protection

Theft, data loss, and data altering were all covered by the confidentiality and data protection procedures.

Data analysis

After the data was collected, it was captured on a computer. The data were analyzed using SPSS version 30, which is a statistical tool for social sciences. Participants' demographic information was analyzed descriptively to obtain frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations. Pearson chi-square tests were used to obtain associations between demographics and non-adherence to ATT. Relationships between risk factors and non-adherence to ATT were obtained by bivariate analysis using logistic regression to obtain odds ratios (ODDs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs). A *p*-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical considerations

Autonomy, justice, non-maleficence, and beneficence were the ethical factors considered. The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki. The protocol was submitted for approval to the Faculty of Medicine and Health Research Ethics Committee at Walter Sisulu University. A protocol number was assigned to the clearance certificate (certificate registration number: 047/2023). The date of issue was 16 August 2023. Prior to obtaining written consent, all participants received complete information about the study through the participant information sheet. After that, each willing participant gave their written informed consent to participate in the study. Participants received assurances regarding data confidentiality.

Results

The results are addressed in the order in which the objectives are presented.

Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants

The socio-demographics determined were gender, age, marital status, educational background, income status, and HIV status. Of the 65 patients with TB, more than half (41, or

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of patients.

Variable categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Males	41	63.08
Females	24	36.92
Total	65	100.00
Age		
18–25	13	20.00
26–35	26	40.00
36–45	14	21.54
46–55	4	6.15
>55	8	12.31
Total	65	100.00
Marital status		
Single	53	81.54
Married	12	18.46
Total	65	100.00
Educational status		
High school	53	81.54
Tertiary level	12	18.46
Total	65	100.00
Income status (ZA)		
Unemployed	35	53.85
1000–3000	12	18.46
3001–5000	9	13.85
>5000	9	13.85
Total	65	100.00
HIV status		
Seropositive	30	46.15
Seronegative	35	53.85
Total	65	100.00

63.08%) were males and 24 (36.92%) were females. Their ages ranged from 18 to 55 years, with a mean age of 2.51 (1–5) with (SD \pm 1.239) years. Less than half of the participants were in the age range of 26–35 (40.00%). The majority were single, 53 (81.53%), and 53 (81.54%) years had a high-school level of education. More than half (35 or 53.854%) were unemployed, and 35 (53.854%) were seronegative (Table 1).

Prevalence of non-adherence to TB treatment

Of the 65 patients who participated in the study, 45 (69.23%) were adherents, while 20 (30.77%) were non-adherents. Of the males, 11 (55.00%) were adherents, and 9 (45.00%) were non-adherents. Gender had a major impact, with males having higher levels of non-adherence (11 or 55.00%) than females, with 9 (45.00%). Results of age distribution revealed higher levels of non-adherence in the 26–35 age range at 10 (50.00%). Non-adherence among single people was higher, with 15 (75.00%), than among married people at 5 (25.00%). Gender was therefore identified as a major variable impacting treatment adherence (Table 2).

Association between socio-demographics and non-adherence

An association between socio-demographics and non-adherence was established. Variables that were asso-

Table 2. Prevalence of adherence and non-adherence of TB patients on TB treatment ($n = 65$).

Variable categories	Treatment adherence and non-adherence	
	Yes	No
Gender		
Male	41 (63.08)	11(55.00)
Female	24 (36.92)	9(45.00)
Age range		
18–25	10(22.22)	3(15.00)
26–35	16(35.56)	10(50.00)
36–45	10(22.22)	4(20.00)
46–55	4(8.89)	0(00.00)
>55	5(11.11)	3(15.00)
Marital status		
Single	38(84.44)	15(75.00)
Married	7(15.56)	5(25.00)
Educational status		
High school	40(88.89)	13(65.00)
Tertial level	5(11.11)	7(35.00)
Income status		
Unemployed	22(48.89)	13(65.00)
1000–3000	6(13.33)	6(30.00)
3001–5000	9(20.00)	0(0.00)
>5000	8(17.78)	1(5.00)
HIV status		
Seropositive	19(42.22)	11(55.00)
Seronegative	26(57.78)	9(45.00)

ciated with non-adherence were gender, with $p < 0.001$, which is statistically significant, and monthly income, with $p = 0.046$, also statistically significant, as reflected in Table 3.

Table 3. Association between socio-demographics and non-adherence ($n = 65$).

Variable categories	Non-adherence			OR (95% CI)	P value
	Yes (n %)	No (%)	Total (n)		
Gender					
Male	19(79.17)	5(20.83)	24	41.84 (16.58–1393.08)	< .0001
Female	1(2.43)	40(97.56)	41		
Age range					
18–25	4(30.77)	9(3.00)	13	3.500 (0.284–43.16)	0.317
26–35	8(26.67)	22(73.33)	30	0.481 (0.079–2.945)	
36–45	3(25.00)	9(75.00)	12	0.625 (0.073–5.350)	
46–55	1(5.00)	1(5.00)	2	–	
>55	4(5.00)	4(5.99)	8	0.500 (0.188–1.332)	
Marital status					
Single	16(30.19)	37(69.81)	53	0.906 (0.227–3.289)	0.831
Married	4(33.33)	8(36.36)	12	1.047 (0.675–0.365)	
Level of education					
High school	15(28.30)	38(71.70)	53	0.553 (0.152–2.018)	0.365
Tertiary level	5(4.67)	7(58.33)	12	0.670 (0.307–1.504)	
Monthly income					
Unemployed	10(28.57)	25(7.42)	35	0.375 (0.066–2.145)	0.047
1000–3000	8(66.67)	4(33.33)	12	0.333 (0.027–4.186)	
3001–5000	1(11.11)	8(88.89)	9	8.000 (1.279–50.000)	
>5000	1(11.11)	8(88.89)	9	8.000 (1.279–50.000)	
HIV status					
Sero positive	9(3.00)	21(70.00)	30	0.935 (0.325–26.93)	0.901
Sero negative	11(31.43)	24(68.57)	35		

Risk factors leading to non-adherence to TB treatment

Furthermore, risk factors leading to non-adherence to TB treatment were established from the patients. The results obtained demonstrated that none were statistically associated with non-adherence, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Risk factors affecting non-adherents on TB treatment.

Risk factor	Non-adherent		Pearson chi-square tests		ODR	95% CI	
	Yes	No	χ^2	P value		Lower-level	Higher level
Side effects	20	44	0.339	0.56	1.368	0.475	3.940
Drug shortage	20	45	0.164	0.735	–	–	–
Staff support	20	45	0.154	0.695	1.294	0.358	4.699
Employee support	14	40	4.931	0.177	–	–	–
Time to get to the clinic	8	17	0.202	0.653	0.675	0.121	3.787

Discussion

Application of theoretical framework in the discussion of results

The theoretical framework helped in explaining the findings from this study. It explains why certain factors are associated with non-adherence to TB treatment. For instance, a finding that patients feel stigmatized might be explained by the social factors of the framework concept or perceived barriers to seeking help.

Summary of key findings

1. Socio-demographics

The total number of patients was 65, with 41 (63.08%) males, the majority 26 (40%) in the age range of 26–35 years; 53 (81.53%) were single; more than half, 53 (81.53%), had a high school level of education; 35 (53.84%) were unemployed; and 35 (53.80%) were seronegative.

2. Prevalence of non-adherents

Non-adherents were 20 (44.00%).

3. Prevalence of non-adherence in socio-demographics on treatment

Male non-adherents accounted for 11 (55.00%). Of the non-adherents, 10 (50%) were in the 26–35 age range, 15 (75.00%) were single, 13 (65.00%) had a high-school education, 13 (65%) were unemployed, and 11 (55%) were seropositive.

4. Patient program and drug-related factors affecting non-adherence

Risk factors affecting non-adherents were distance from the clinic, lack of family and staff support, poverty, ad-

verse drug effects, and drug shortages, but these were all not statistically significant.

Interpretation of the results

The prevalence of non-adherence to anti-TB therapy was 20%. This result was consistent with research done in Ethiopia with a prevalence of 20% non-adherence to anti-TB therapy reported in studies with systematic reviews finding pooled prevalence rates around 21.3% and 20% (Nezenega et al. 2020). However, Zhang et al. (2020) state that different regions and time periods in China show TB treatment non-adherence rates often exceeding 20%, sometimes significantly higher, with specific studies in 2015, 2018, and 2016 reporting non-adherence rates of 21.2%, 36.0%, and 33.63%, respectively.

These high rates are attributed to factors like internal migration, out-of-pocket expenses for treatment, lack of family or social support, and limited TB knowledge, particularly among vulnerable groups such as internal migrants. According to Gashu et al. (2021), research conducted in 2021 found that adherence was low, particularly during the continuation phase, and reports from North-west Ethiopia indicate significant rates of non-adherence to TB treatment.

Forgetfulness, being away from home, the distance from medical facilities, anxiety about medication side effects, and lengthy waiting periods at health centers are the main causes of this non-adherence. Variations in participant characteristics, the duration of adherence assessment, accessibility to healthcare facilities, and problems with adherence owing to the adverse effects and high pill load might all contribute to this discrepancy between studies.

The prevalence of non-adherents was low at 20 (44.00%), with more male adherents. Adherence to treatment by TB patients was not associated with most demographic characteristics, such as age, marital status, educational status, and HIV status. Shinde et al. (2024) argue that while some studies show demographic factors such as age and marital status having an impact on TB treatment adherence, others find these characteristics are not significant predictors of non-adherence. Instead, adherence is frequently linked to other variables such as socioeconomic status, drug side effects, HIV co-infection, and support from healthcare providers and family. However, some research indicates that specific demographics, such as a certain age group (e.g., younger than 35 years), or having family support and adequate education, can improve adherence.

In this study, non-adherence was substantially correlated with gender ($X^2 = 0.865, p < 0.001$). This is a socio-demographic cross-sectional study. This design cannot prove causality because many studies identify being female as a risk factor for higher non-adherence in chronic diseases, such as cardiovascular issues, diabetes, and HIV treatment. The association is driven by factors such as side effects, in which women report more adverse drug reactions (ADRs), leading to voluntary discontinuation. Furthermore, in terms of cost/resources, women often experience

more cost-related barriers, as well as caregiving roles, in that increased caregiving demands can lead to prioritizing others' health over their own. Therefore, the gender association is not that "being a woman causes non-adherence" but that social, biological, and economic factors linked to gender are associated with it.

This finding aligns with a study conducted by Niyokwizera et al. (2024), which revealed that patient-related non-adherence is significantly influenced by demographic factors (age, gender, marital status, occupation, family and social support), substance abuse, and beliefs about mental illness.

In this study, non-adherence was also substantially correlated with unemployment ($X^2 = 10.604, p < 0.014$). Once again, this study being cross-sectional, in terms of association, studies show a strong, positive link between unemployment and non-adherence. In terms of the causal mechanism, the connection is likely indirect. Unemployment leads to financial strain, which causes cost-related non-adherence (inability to afford medication). Furthermore, confounding factors such as depression (common among the unemployed) or lack of health insurance are the actual drivers of non-adherence, rather than just the unemployment status itself.

The findings of this study showed that 20 (44.00%) of the TB patients were not following their prescribed treatment. This result is in line with related research conducted by Pedersen et al. (2023) that concludes that non-adherence to TB treatment is a significant global health challenge, as it can lead to treatment failure, drug resistance, and increased transmission of the disease.

Results from this study demonstrated that one socio-demographic factor that was shown to be substantially linked to non-adherence to TB treatment was unemployment ($p = 0.014$). Gwalani et al. (2025), in their specific study, highlighted unemployment as a significant socio-demographic factor that increases the risk of patients not following their medication regimen. This finding is consistent with broader research suggesting that socioeconomic challenges such as joblessness, poverty, and homelessness are major obstacles to successful TB treatment, requiring comprehensive strategies to address these multifactorial issues.

Treatment failure is indeed associated with socioeconomic challenges such as poverty and the inability to afford medications, alongside a lack of social support and negative interactions within the therapeutic setting. These factors, which are social and economic determinants of health, create barriers that impede successful treatment outcomes by affecting adherence, engagement, and the overall therapeutic environment. Addressing these interconnected issues requires multi-sectoral approaches involving not just healthcare but also social services, housing, and employment to improve health equity.

According to this research, the largest incidence of missed medicine doses was seen among patients whose yearly income was much below the national average. These results are consistent with the results of a study conducted by Wu et al. (2024), who concluded that, despite the Chinese 2005 implementation of the DOTS program for TB

treatment, patients still face significant financial burdens. These are due to costs beyond the free medication provided, such as out-of-pocket expenses for additional medical tests, transportation, and the loss of income from lost workdays. These indirect and non-medical costs, alongside variations in the Basic Medical Insurance (BMI) coverage, contribute to high financial problems for patients.

In this cross-sectional study design, results revealed that family support was one of the factors affecting non-ATT. In this case, a socio-demographic factor associated with medication non-adherence, family support is generally not regarded as a definitive, isolated causal factor but rather as a critical psychosocial variable that is strongly associated with better adherence.

This outcome is consistent with earlier research conducted in India by Shimange et al. (2025), which highlighted the crucial role of family involvement in treatment supervision for individuals with mental illnesses, with families often acting as the primary caregivers and providing essential emotional and practical support to promote treatment adherence and recovery.

It was established in the current study that single TB patients had higher non-adherence rates than married or divorced people. Once again, in this cross-sectional study design of socio-demographic factors associated with tuberculosis (TB) treatment non-adherence, being single is generally regarded as an associated factor (a potential risk factor) rather than a direct, demonstrated cause of non-adherence. Such studies, which are often cross-sectional, can only demonstrate associations, not causality. Being single (or unmarried) is frequently associated with higher rates of non-adherence, often due to a lack of social support (e.g., no family members to remind them to take medication).

This is consistent with findings from a study conducted by Chen et al. (2020), which showed that single TB patients have higher non-adherence rates and that family support improves treatment outcomes. These results are consistent with the broader scientific literature, which emphasizes the crucial role of family members in monitoring and supporting TB treatment to ensure medication adherence and treatment success.

In the findings of this study, which is cross-sectional, substance abuse influenced the patient's failure to comply with their TB treatment. In studies of socio-demographic factors associated with treatment non-adherence, substance abuse is generally treated as a risk factor that shows strong, consistent associations rather than definitive, direct causality.

While many studies describe substance abuse as a "cause" or "contributor" to non-adherence, the research methodology – often cross-sectional – usually only allows researchers to demonstrate that substance abuse is a significant correlated factor or predictor of non-adherence, not that it is the sole, exclusive cause.

A study examining drug use, smoking, and non-adherence to medication, Ge et al. (2023) found no statistically significant link between drug use, smoking, and non-adherence to medication, though other factors like depression or socioeconomic status might influence them. Other research has found significant links between non-adherence and

factors such as depression, illicit drug use, and alcohol use, demonstrating the complex nature of medication adherence.

Findings from this study on patient programs, such as distance from the clinic and related drug factors, such as side effects, were factors affecting non-adherence. This is supported by Chauke et al. (2022), who indicated that factors such as medication side effects and drug-related issues (such as stock outages) and patient-related issues, such as distances to care facilities, are indeed known to affect medication adherence.

Strengths and limitations of this study

Strengths

- Studying targeted TB patients at a PHC allows a deeper understanding of their challenges and feasible interventions.
- Identifying risk factors for non-adherence will target better resources and treatments.
- Potential for action to improve adherence, potentially leading to better treatment outcomes.
- Descriptive data on the prevalence of non-adherents and socio-demographics are provided.
- Research focuses on specific factors assessing the impact on adherence.

Limitations

- Convenience sampling coupled with a small sample size creates difficulty in generalizing results to a wider population. The most significant disadvantage of convenience sampling is that it often fails to represent the broader population accurately. Because participants are selected based on their availability rather than through a randomized process, the sample may be biased toward certain groups or characteristics. Therefore, the main observed issue with convenience sampling in regression analysis is not necessarily wider confidence intervals, but rather that the intervals are invalid for making inferences about the general population because of inherent, unquantifiable bias.
- The study sample size of 65 instead of the planned 86 participants is a limitation because a small sample size limits the reliability of the study by reducing statistical power, making it hard to detect true effects (increasing Type II errors/false negatives) and risking false positives because of random chance, leading to unstable, imprecise results (wide confidence intervals) that are difficult to generalize to the larger population (poor external validity) and may not represent its diversity, reducing the external validity and statistical power of the findings.
- Patient self-reporting of missed doses may be subject to social desirability bias, underreporting, or recall bias.
- The data used were from a single-site or small-sample study. This may not be generalizable to the broader population. The study findings may highlight the need for interventions that cater to specific

socio-demographic groups identified as more prone to non-adherence.

- Identifying and addressing social barriers that can improve treatment adherence.

Recommendations

- Since males have been mentioned to be more non-adherent to ATT, future studies on non-adherence should focus on males.
- Comprehensive health education programs should be developed for TB patients and families to increase awareness of TB and its treatment.
- Establish social support groups to provide emotional and practical assistance to TB patients.
- Create effective communication between healthcare providers and patients to emphasize empathy and understanding.
- Increase public knowledge about TB to lessen the stigma attached to the illness.
- Strengthen DOT programs to ensure that patients take their medications as prescribed.

Based on this study examining socio-demographic contributions to TB treatment, the following conclusion is provided.

Conclusion

Non-adherence to TB treatment is driven by a complex interplay of socioeconomic and demographic factors rather than a single cause. Key, consistent drivers of treatment default include extreme poverty/income insecurity, high transportation costs, long distances to treatment centers, and lack of social or family support. Additionally, younger age, low educational attainment, and male gender are significant, high-risk socio-demographic indicators for defaulting during the treatment continuation phase.

The following are the key takeaways:

- Economic barriers: Inability to afford travel and food for clinic visits, often exacerbated by job loss because of illness, is the primary driver of default.
- Social and family support: Lack of family support and social stigma significantly increase the risk of default.
- Geographical access: Distance to clinics and limited access to transportation make frequent Directly Observed Treatment Strategy (DOTS) visits difficult.

References

Amiri H, Mohammadi MJ, Alavi SM, Salmanzadeh S, Hematnia F, Azar M, Rahmatinsi H (2021) Capture-recapture based study on the completeness of smear positive pulmonary tuberculosis reporting in southwest Iran during 2016. *BMC Public Health* 21: e2318. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-12398-w>

- Patient demographics: Males, younger patients, and those with lower educational levels are more prone to defaulting.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflicts of interest are disclosed by the writer. The study design, data collection, analysis, and interpretation, article preparation, and the choice to publish the findings were all done independently of the sponsors. Because of ethical or privacy concerns, the research data is not available.

Ethical statements

The author declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The study was conducted according to the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki. The protocol was sent for approval to the Faculty of Medicine and Health Research Ethics Committee at Walter Sisulu University. A protocol number was assigned to the clearance certificate (certificate registration number: 047/2023). The date of issue was 16 August 2023.

The author declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in this study. Written informed consent was obtained from the patients to publish this paper.

The author declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

LNKK: Project management, supervision, validation, visualization, investigation, methodology, and formal analysis. Writing – first draft, writing – editing and review. The published version of the work has been reviewed and approved by the author.

Author ORCIDs

Lucky Norah Katende-Kyenda <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5398-3253>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

Arakelyan S, Karat AS, Jones ASK, Vidal N, Stagg HR, Darvell M (2021) Relational dynamics of treatment behavior among individuals with tuberculosis in high-income countries: A scoping review. *Patient Preference Adherence* 15: 2137–2154. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S313633>

- Biru D, Woldeamayem EM (2020) Determinants of drug-resistant tuberculosis in southern Ethiopia: A case-control study. *Infectious Drug Resistance* 13: e1823. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S256536>
- CDC [Center for Disease Control] (2025) Tuberculosis. Clinical Overview of Tuberculosis Disease. <https://www.cdc.gov/tb/hcp/clinical-overview/tuberculosis-disease.html> [accessed on 7 September 2025]
- Chauke GD, Nakwafila O, Chibi B, Sartorius B, Mashamba-Thompson T (2022) Factors influencing poor medication adherence amongst patients with chronic disease in low-and-middle-income countries: A systematic scoping review. *Heylon* 8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.he-lyon.2022.e09716>
- Chen X, Du L, Wu R, Xu H, Ji Y, Zhang Y, Zhu X (2020) The effects of family, society and national policy support on treatment adherence among newly diagnosed tuberculosis patients: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Infectious Disease* 20: e623. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-020-05354-3>
- Falzon D, Zignol M, Bastard M, Floyd K, Kasaeva T (2023) The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the global tuberculosis epidemic. *Frontiers in Immunology* 14: e1234785. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2023.1234785>
- Faye LM, Hosu MC, Apalata T (2024) Drug-resistant tuberculosis in rural eastern cape, South Africa: A study of patients' characteristics in selected healthcare facilities. *International Journal of Environmental Research in Public Health* 21: e1594. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21121594>
- Gashu KD, Gelaye KA, Tilahun B (2021) Adherence to TB treatment remains low during continuation phase among adult patients in Northwest Ethiopia. Adherence to TB treatment remains low during continuation phase among adult patients in Northwest Ethiopia. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 21: e725. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-021-06428-6>
- Ge L, Heng BH, Yapm CW (2023) Understanding reasons and determinants of medication non-adherence in community-dwelling adults: A cross-sectional study comparing young and older age groups. *BMC Health Services Research* 23: e905. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-023-09904-8>
- Gebremariam RB, Wolde M, Beyene A (2021) Determinants of adherence to anti-TB treatment and associated factors among adult TB patients in Gondar city administration, Northwest, Ethiopia: Based on health belief model perspective. *Journal of Health Population Nutrition* 40: 1–49. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41043-021-00275-6>
- Gwalani R, Shah H, Saxena D, Patel J, Baliyan S, Thakur J, Rai S, Sen A, Yadav A (2025) Barriers and facilitators of adherence to anti-TB treatment in Western Indian population: A cross-sectional study. *Indian Journal of Tuberculosis*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijtb.2025.06.019>
- Johnson C (2025) Slovin's Formula Calculator 2025. <https://dissertation-dataanalysishelp.com/slovin-s-formula-calculator/> [accessed on 16 August 2025]
- Kamangu JWN, Mboweni SH (2024) Factors impacting ART adherence among HIV-Positive older adolescents and younger adults in Namibia: A qualitative analysis. *The Open Public Health Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0118749445299654240402033559>
- Kamolwat P, Nateniyom S, Chairprasert A, Disratthakit A, Mahasirimongkol S, Yamada N (2021) Prevalence and associated risk factors of drug-resistant tuberculosis in Thailand: results from the fifth national anti-tuberculosis drug resistance survey. *Tropical Medicine and International Health* 26: 45–53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tmi.13502>
- Karat AS, Jones ASK, Abubakar I, Campbell, CNJ, Clarke, AL, Clarke CS (2021) “You have to change your whole life”: A qualitative study of the dynamics of treatment adherence among adults with tuberculosis in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Clinical Tuberculosis and Other Mycobacterial Diseases* 23: e100233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jctube.2021.100233>
- Katende-Kyenda LN (2025) Determinants of non-adherence to anti-tuberculosis treatment in a public primary healthcare clinic in South Africa: Improving the quality of long-term care. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 22: e1209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph22081209>
- Leketa MM, Zondi S, Cele L, Mathibe M, Ngwepe P (2024) Factors associated with unfavorable treatment outcomes among tuberculosis patients at health facilities of Maseru, Lesotho. *South African Family Practice* 66: a6004. <https://doi.org/10.4102/safp.v66i1.6004>
- Mom Z, Li X, Zhai Y, Mo Z, Li X, Zhai Y, Men Y, Tang Y, Qiao J, Jia X, Huang Y, Wang B (2023) Reliability and validity of a questionnaire measuring knowledge, attitude and practice regarding “oil, salt and sugar” among canteen staff. *Scientific Reports* 13: e20442. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-47804-3>
- Nezenega ZS, Perimal-Lewis L, Maeder AJ (2020) Factors influencing patient adherence to tuberculosis treatment in Ethiopia: A literature review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17: E5626. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17155626>
- Nidoi J, Muttamba W, Walusimbi S, Imoko JF, Lochoro P (2021) Impact of socio-economic factors on Tuberculosis treatment outcomes in north-eastern Uganda: a mixed methods study. *BMC Public Health* 1: e2167. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-12056-1>
- Niyokwizera E, Nitunga D, Muhumuza J, Niyubahwe RMI, Abamara NC, Kirabira J (2024) Personality traits and other factors associated with psychotropic medication non-adherence at two hospitals in Uganda. A cross-sectional study. *PLoS ONE* 9: e0302350. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0302350>
- Oamen BR (2024) Tuberculosis treatment adherence among tuberculosis patients: Insights from a cross-sectional study in the Eastern Cape, South Africa. *Africa Journal of Nursing and Midwifery* 26: 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.25159/2520-5293/17413>
- Omar AA, Mohamoud JH, Adam MH, Garba B, Hassan MA, Mohamed IA, Adam ZM (2024) Assessment of non-adherence to anti-TB drugs and associated factors among patients attending TB treatment centers during COVID-19 pandemic in Mogadishu, Somalia: A cross-sectional study. *Infection and Drug Resistance* 17: 3879–3890. <https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S468985>
- Pan American Health Organization [PAHO] (2024) Tuberculosis resurges as top infectious disease killer. Pan American Health Organization, World Health Organization. <https://www.paho.org/en/news/1-11-2024-tuberculosis-resurges-top-infectious-disease-killer#> [Accessed on 7th July 2025]
- Pedersen OS, Holmgaard FB, Mikkelsen MKD, Lange C, Sotgiu G, Lillebaek T, Andersen AB, Wejse CM, Dahl VN (2023) Global treatment outcomes of extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis in adults: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Infection* 87: 177–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2023.06.014>
- Ranganathan B, Caduf C, Frampton CMA (2024) Designing and validating a research questionnaire – Part 2. *Perspective Clinical Research* 15: 42–45. https://doi.org/10.4103/picr.picr_318_23 [Epub 2024. PMID: 38282630; PMCID: PMC10810057]

- Religioni U, Barrios-Rodríguez R, Requena P, Borowska M, Ostrowski J (2025) Enhancing therapy adherence: Impact on clinical outcomes, healthcare costs, and patient quality of life. *Medicina* 61(1): e153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina61010153>
- Shimange ME, Shilubane HN, Rikhotso TN (2025) An explorative study on the role of family members in caring for mental health care users in South Africa. *Journal of Psychiatric and Mental Health Nursing* 32: 854–863. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpm.13161>
- Shinde AM (2024) Socio-demographic factors & adherence of newly diagnosed pulmonary tuberculosis patients to the newly introduced daily regimen: A hospital survey based follow up study. *Indian Journal of Tuberculosis*: S250–S257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijtb.2024.03.011>
- Tirore LL, Ersido T, Handiso TB, Areba AS (2024) Non-adherence to anti-tuberculosis treatment and associated factors among TB patients in public health facilities of Hossana town, Southern Ethiopia, 2022. *Frontiers in Medicine* 7: e1360351. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2024.1360351>
- Unni E, Bae S (2022) Exploring a new theoretical model to explain the behavior of medication adherence. *Pharmacy* 10: 1–43. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmacy10020043>
- WHO [World Health Organization] (2023) Global trend in case notifications of people newly diagnosed with TB, 2010–2022. <https://www.who.int/teams/global-programme-on-tuberculosis-and-lung-health/tb-reports/global-tuberculosis-report-2023/tb-diagnosis> [Accessed on 2nd September 2025]
- WHO [World Health Organization] (2024a) Global Tuberculosis Report. <https://www.google.com/search?q=WHO+Global+TB+Report%2C+2024&rlz=> [Accessed on 8 September 2025]
- WHO [World Health Organization] (2024b) Global TB Report. 1.1 TB Incidence. <https://www.who.int/teams/global-programme-on-tuberculosis-and-lung-health/tb-reports/global-tuberculosis-report-2024/tb-disease-burden/1-1-tb-incidence#> [Accessed on 9 September 2025]
- WHO [World Health Organization] (2025) National TB Recovery Plan 4.0 April 2025 – March 2026. https://www.health.gov.za/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/TB-Recovery-Plan-4_final_250526-1.pdf [Accessed on 8 September 2025]
- Wu Z, Yu Y, Xie F, Chen Q, Cao Z, Chen S, Liu GG (2024) Economic burden of patients with leading cancers in China: A cost-of-illness study. *BMC Health Service Research* 24: e1135. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-024-11514-x>
- Yene F, Bantie B, Yilma T, Zinab I, Animen S (2025) Non-prescribed drug use and its associated factors among pregnant women in Southwest Ethiopia. *Science Report* 15: e22851. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-80247-y> [PMID: 40595740; PMCID: PMC12217442]
- Zereabruk K, Kahsay T, Teklemichael H, Aberhe W, Hailay A, Mebrahtom G, Bezabh G (2024) Determinants of multi-drug-resistant tuberculosis among adults undergoing treatment for tuberculosis in Tigray Region, Ethiopia: a case-control study. *BMJ Open Respiratory Research* 11: e001999. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjresp-2023-001999> [PMID: 38697676; PMCID: PMC11086502]
- Zhang J, Yang Y, Qiao X, Wang L, Bai J, Yangchen T, Chodron P (2020) Factors influencing medication nonadherence to pulmonary tuberculosis treatment in Tibet, China: A qualitative study from the patient perspective. *Patient Preference and Adherence* 14: 1149–1158. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PPA.S252448>